

NON-IDEALLY ANISOTROPIC SOLIDS BEHAVIOR UNDER GENERALIZED STRESS

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ABSTRACT

Experimental studies of hardwood disclose the complexity of mechanical behavior of such natural porous composites,including pronounced different anisotropy types,very marked sign sensitivity,isotropic and generalized stresses effects,appearance of different deformation and failure modes.The structural isotropy group generally assumed which is widely used in Engineering as well as a rhombic symmetry group or a texture to one only privileged direction,is no longer adequate to predict properly the actual directional state of this class of materials.An analysis of isotropy group evolution and a behavior modelization of non-ideally anisotropic solids are proposed which account for the different observed phenomena.

Keywords : Anisotropy."Off-axis" tests.Triaxial tests.Symmetry group.Isotropy group.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that during drying process the internal structure of wood becomes strongly oriented : thus anisotropy.On the macroscopic level the internal oriented structure results in the anisotropy of the mechanical behavior.For wood the internal structure generally presents three orthogonal privileged directions of symmetry : axial direction L,radial direction R and tangential direction T corresponding to the growth process of the tree.The macroscopic behavior is generally thus assumed to be orthotropic.

When wood is subjected to further irreversible processes the anisotropy of the internal is modified.The modifications affect not only the degree of initial anisotropy but also the type of anisotropy,according to the orientation of the principal directions of the irreversible deformation with respect to the mecanosorptive processes during drying.

Natural materials such as consolidated soils,stratified rocks,drying woods,bones,...as well as artificial materials such as composites with brittle or ductile matrix,ceramics,...are characterized by internal oriented structures at different ranges of scale.These structures change under permanent sollicitations (deformation,fluid flow,heat and mass transfer) manifest in a directional response to agencies and influence the overall material behavior.

We present a theoretical and experimental study of oakwood mechanical behavior under compression tests with different rates of confining pressure.The

structural isotropic group is assumed to be a rhombic symmetry group which admits the three orthogonal privileged directions L,R,T (ideal orthotropic solid). Attention is stressed on the evolution of the anisotropy of structure. An experimental program is developed in order to assess the directional compression deformations under confining pressure at different rates. The initial values and the evolution of the anisotropic material constants involved in the proposed model are thus determined.

2. GENERAL APPROACH

Consider an orthotropic solid for which the orthogonal privileged directions $(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \mathbf{v}_3)$ correspond respectively to the radial, tangential and longitudinal directions (R,T,L) of wood (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Privileged directions of wood and associated orthotropic solid.

The material internal structure is invariant under the orthotropic group Σ :

$$\Sigma = \{ \pm I, S_1, S_2, S_3 \} \quad (1)$$

where S_1, S_2, S_3 are reflections with respect to the $(\mathbf{v}_2, \mathbf{v}_3), (\mathbf{v}_3, \mathbf{v}_1), (\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2)$ planes.

Consider the tensors $\mathbf{M}_i = \mathbf{v}_i \otimes \mathbf{v}_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ and their invariance group M : the group M of orthogonal transformations such that $\mathbf{Q} \in M$ if and only if :

$$\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{M}_i\mathbf{Q}^t = \mathbf{M}_i \quad (2)$$

It is easily proved that $\Sigma = M$. The invariant properties of the material internal structure are identical with those of the tensors \mathbf{M} . Thus the tensors \mathbf{M} are the structural tensors for an ideally orthotropic solid.

Within the framework of Non-Linear Continuum Mechanics and the Theory of representation for tensor functions, the constitutive relation of an orthotropic material such as oakwood relates the stress tensor \mathbf{T} to an agency tensor \mathbf{D} . This relation is expressed by :

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{M}_1, \mathbf{M}_2, \mathbf{M}_3) \quad (3)$$

since constitutive laws must involve the material structural tensors.

With the Principle of isotropy of space which requires that an arbitrary transformation \mathbf{Q} of the full orthogonal group O and applied to both the material and the agency results in the same transformation of the material response, thus we have for all $\mathbf{Q} \in O$:

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{M}_i\mathbf{Q}) = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{F}\mathbf{Q} \quad (4)$$

Considering Equations (2) and (4). It is easily proved that $Q \in \Sigma$ if and only if :

$$F(QDQ^t, M) = QFQ^t \quad (5)$$

Representation theorems for tensors functions [1-2] furnish an invariant form for Equation (3) :

$$\begin{cases} T = a_1 I + a_2 M_1 + a_3 M_2 + a_4 M_3 + a_5 D + a_6 D^2 + \\ a_7 (M_1 D + D M_1) + a_8 (M_2 D + D M_2) + a_9 (M_3 D + D M_3) \\ a_i = a_i (\text{tr } M_k D, \text{tr } M_k D^2, \text{tr } D^3), (i = 1, \dots, 9), (k = 1, 2, 3) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The aim of this work is not to describe an entire development of this application but is only to focus the attention on the involvement of structural tensors M_k with the agency tensor D as it is seen in Equation (6). It is thus helpfully to characterize solids by oriented tests with respect to the axis of the material.

Consider triaxial tests that consist of axial compression σ on oriented specimens subjected to confining pressures p . Denote by θ the angle between the axis of the specimens and the privileged axis v_2 in the planes (R,T) and (T,L), the privileged axis v_1 in the plane (L,R), (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Angle θ of specimens in the privileged planes.

The arguments of Equation (6) can be expressed in terms of the three parameters σ, p and θ .

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Testing procedure

A number of tests have been performed [3] consisting of directional axial compression under different confining pressures on oriented specimens of a chopped oakwoodcut. Specimens with a cylindrical regular shape were cut in seven different directions $\theta = 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75$ and 90° , where θ is the angle between the axis of the specimen and the direction v_1 in the (L,R) plane, the direction v_2 in the (R,T) and (T,L) planes. The number of orientations within those three planes amounts to 18 (Figure 3a). The sizes of the specimens are presented on the Figure 3b.

Using a triaxial cell the compression tests under confining pressure were carried out with respect of three different pressures : $p = 0, 10$ and 20 MPa. Four to five tests were performed for each orientation and each confining pressure. The tests were stopped during the hardening of the samples while other irreversible deformations appeared.

Figure 3.a.Orientations of the chopped oakwoodcut samples
b.Sample sizes.

3.2.Deformation modes

The compression tests under confining pressure performed on oakwood showed an evolution of the material behavior with either the lateral pressure p and the orientation θ of the samples in the privileged planes.

As shown in the Figure 4, the strain-stress curves in the privileged directions R,T,L give a short outline about the rheological behavior of oakwood only regarding to the uniaxial compression. It is essentially elastic-perfectly plastic in the direction R, plastic with strain hardening in the direction T and elastic-brittle in the direction L.

For all that the behavior is more generally elastic-perfectly plastic for all "off-axis" orientations at low pressure ($p = 0$ MPa). The plastic flow evolves with the lateral pressure. The behavior of oakwood tested in compression under confining pressure is elastic with strain hardening at higher pressures ($p = 10$ and 20 MPa).

The Figure 5 shows the anisotropy of the yield stress (elastic limit) for each lateral pressure regarding to the orientations of the samples in the three privileged planes. The first remark that we can make is that the degree of the yield stress anisotropy of oakwood is strongly influenced under the confining pressure. A second remark and otherwise the most important concerns the evolution of both the type and the degree of the elastic anisotropy of oakwood. Hence we can explain the irreversible deformations that we observed on the samples tested under confining pressures $p = 10$ and 20 MPa : the samples pulled out from the triaxial cell, initially as a straight circular cylinder, showed inclinations and elliptic transversal sections (Figure 6). Such irreversible deformations (inclination in a one direction and ellipses) were already observed on an transversal isotropic rock [4].

The works performed on oakwood in order to reveal the influence of orientation upon its mechanical behavior were realized in considering oakwood ideally orthotropic. Thus the symmetry axis which characterize an orthotropic medium must coincide necessarily with the privileged axis of oakwood (the longitudinal, radial and tangential directions) that occur during the growth process of oak tree. Our results do to come into sight that oakwood holds other symmetries which influence the behavior. Oakwood is not ideally orthotropic.

Figure 4. Mechanical anisotropy of oakwood.

Figure 5. Yield stress anisotropy
 a. $p = 0$ MPa. b. $p = 10$ MPa
 c. $p = 20$ MPa.

Figure 6. Transformed samples under confining pressure .

4. Discussion. [5]

4.1. Some geometrical remarks

4.1.1. If G is a characteristic symmetry group of a body, we can associate the isotropy group M of a simple solid such as an orthogonal transformation Q applied to the material preserves the invariance. It is easily seen that $G \subset M$. The groups M are known. It results that G is either a finite group or a texture.

4.1.2. Suppose the studied body as such as an ideal homogeneous solid. We can define a stratification S of this solid such as S_i is a i -dimensional strata. Suppose that the solid is invariant in the symmetry G_i of this strata for all point $M \in S_i - S_{i-1}$. G_i is not necessarily constant along a strata. For all that, we have : $G_i \subset G_{i-1}$.

4.1.3. Application.

Consider a material revolution cylinder of axis S_1 . We denote S_3 the cylinder without the axis S_1 . In all point $M \in S_3$, the symmetry group is a finite group (C_4C_2), while in a point M located on S_1 , the symmetry group is not finite.

Now, we consider a material elliptic basis cylinder of axis S_1 . We denote S_2 the set of the two planes of symmetry without the axis S_1 , and S_3 the cylinder without S_1 and S_2 . In all point $M \in S_3$, the symmetry group is a finite group (C_2C_1). For a point located in S_2 , the group is a finite group (C_4C_2). For a point located on S_1 , the group is a finite group (D_2'). We have :

$$C_2C_1 \subset C_4C_2 \subset D_2' \quad (7)$$

Each subgroup is a 2-index group in the next. This cylinder is the transformed revolution cylinder with a loss of generators.

Finally consider this last cylinder with an inclination of its axis. We preserve the same stratification. For all point $M \in S_3$, the symmetry group is finite (C_1). In a point located in S_2 , the group is finite (C_2C_1). For a point M located on S_1 , the group is finite (C_4C_2). We have :

$$C_1 \subset C_2C_1 \subset C_4C_2 \quad (8)$$

Each subgroup is a 2-index group in the next. This cylinder is obtained with a loss of generators with respect to the precedent.

These stratifications concern the Group of Geometry. The isotropy groups are against associated to the solids. It is possible that the deformations set to fit these two structure in the aim to assure their compatibility.

4.2. Non-ideally anisotropic solids

Let be M the isotropy group of the mechanical behavior, G_i the symmetry groups associated to the different strates of an ideal solid and \bar{G}_i the groups associated to the real body. We can easily prove that :

$$\bar{G}_i \subset G_i \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{G}_i \subset G \subset M. \quad (10)$$

The groups G_i are known. A bilinear form is associated to the group G_0 . We suppose that G will be the group "the biggest" associated to this bilinear form, or one or more of its "stables" subgroups.

When $G_0 \subset M$, a contradiction appears with $G \subset M$. The deformations of the solid are at that time those of a solid whom the obvious material symmetries will be the groups \bar{G}_i .

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